

Qualitative Study on Sustainable Girl Child Education at Middle School Level of Education in Mirriah, Niger Republic

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Abstract

This study was carried out to investigate factors influencing girl child' education sustainability at middle school level of education in Mirriah. Two rural middle schools in Mirriah were selected at random to conduct this study. A sample of twenty-four participants among whom seven unschooled girls, seven out-of-school girls, five administrators, and five COGES members were selected purposively. A qualitative grounded theory was used to conduct this study. The general objective of this research was to assess the degree of peer influence on girl child education in rural middle schools. The specific objectives were formulated as follow: to investigate the influence of out-of-schooled peers and unschooled peers on girl child education in Gogo and Fotoro middle schools. The data were collected through direct interviews and the results revealed that peers in general have some levels of negative influence on girl child education. It was concluded that unschooled peers have a high negative influence on the girl child education that's why recommendations related to the parents' follow up and the choice of friendship were addressed.

Keywords: Girls child education, out-of-school, influence, rural area.

Introduction

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948, as cited in Yacine, 2015, p.54), "Everyone has the right to education" (Art.26, para.1). "Education is the process through which individuals acquire adequate and appropriate knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and behaviour necessary to function optimally as a citizen" stated by (Boonprasert, 2010, as cited in Rachel 2013, p.25). It is evident that education is the most formidable weapon to transform or develop a country because the place where education progresses, ignorance withdraws. In this sense, no nation can develop without qualitative education of its citizens, especially female citizens. According to the popular adage, "educate a man, and you educate an individual, but educate a woman and you educate a nation". Thus, girls' education is a fundamental aspect in the development of a nation. This adage is supported by Puri (2016, p. 1) when she said, "Girls' education is like sowing the seed which gives rise to a revitalized, cheerful and full-grown family plant". This explains the fact that education of the girl-child is a key factor in the development of a country, communities and individuals. In this case, girls' education contributes to the improvement of the maternal health, the reduction of infant death, and ensures a good family education. However, the girls' education cannot find its full meaning only when there is good school retention. The issue of keeping girls at school continues to be a topic of discussion (Ahmed, 2013; Mnguni, 2014; Amelie, 2015; Abungu, 2015; Puri, 2016; Johannes, 2018; Abdou, 2020; Mohamed, 2022; Bogosi, 2021). Indeed, "the poor school retention of girls continues to impact their academic results and often causes their permanent drop out from school in rural areas in Niger" (Sani, 2020, p.12). In this respect, according to the Ministry of Education and Professional Training of Niger republic (MEPT, 2020), "the rural population is much more affected by this phenomenon. This population accounts for nearly 80% of the whole country's population" (p.12, para2).

In the education framework, school retention constitutes the second issue after that of enrollment. This place offers to this issue a very remarkable importance in education. Nowadays, despite the big number of the societies which recognize the importance of girls' education, the question of sustainable education remains so problematic. Abungu (2015, as cited in Sani, 2020) mentions that "In almost all developing countries, School dropout, and retention rate has been a subject of interest to

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academics, researchers and policy makers for a long time” (p. 2). The matter of retaining girls at school has been widely discussed in the research world: (Ahmed, 2013; Mnguni, 2014; Amelie, 2015; Abungu, 2015; UNESCO, 2015; Puri, 2016; Juhannes, 2018; Lokonon, 2018; Bogosi, 2021; Mohamed, 2022; etc.). Many are the factors that influence the school retention of girls (Abungu, 2015; Espace Femmes, 2019; Abdou, 2020; Bogosi, 2021). One among those factors is the peer influence. According to Bogosi (2021) “peer group influence has a negative and positive effect in modelling the behaviour of students and their academic performance” (p. 69).

Peer pressures among students are of various natures. Ombuya et al. (2012) and Rumberge (2001) identified three main categories of peer influence that can lead to dropout. These include: Outside influences-brought by friends and peer pressure from other secondary school dropouts, lack of interest in gaining education and teen pregnancies which has accounted for a higher percentage of girls who drop out of secondary schools. These categories can only be managed by the head of the institutions with the support of the parents and other education stakeholders. A cross sectional study conducted by Omollo and Yambo (2017) revealed that peer pressure influenced student drop out was at 43.75%. High dropout was as a result of parent/guardian financial status and family headship which lead to inadequate guidance/ mentorship to the students. The study concluded that in most cases where students are most often sent home there are high chances that some never returned to school and most schools did not support the learners who were coming from poor background. It can therefore be concluded that socio-economic factors highly influence the retention of students in secondary school. Other studies by Duflo, Pascalia, and Michael (2010), Yambo and Tuitoek (2014) on gender gaps in education also realized that adolescent pregnancy brought by peer influence mostly results in the dropping out of girls’ and their continuity to secondary school education. Many of such girls end up in marriage or abandoned at home without any academic achievement realized. Similarly, boys are equally endangered because when they drop out of school they engage in some activities which are detrimental to their dear lives and prone to poor.

The issue of school enrolment and retention has also been discussed (INS, 2006; SUD Education, 2013; Espace Femmes, 2019; Abdou, 2020). These studies found that the academic repetition and the drop out of the students constitute the negative consequences of low school retention of students. This social phenomenon of school retention can be seen through three major indicators in Niger. The first one is the national rate of academic level repetition of the students present. Data from DRES/Zinder (2020), revealed that the national rate of the academic repetition in middle school of the past six years shows that there is weak school retention especially for girls from 2013 to 2018.

Table 1: National rate of academic repetition in Niger

Gender/Years	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Boys	20.4	21.5	18.9	20.6	22.8	25.9
Girls	21.2	22	18.2	20.4	22	25.8
Total	20.7	21.7	18.6	20.5	22.4	25.8

Source: DRES/Zinder (2020)

The second indicator that displays the weak school retention is the national rate of school completion. In spite of the progressive rate of the school completion from 2013 to 2018, this rate remains low and can be explained by the permanent and temporary dropout of the students.

Table 2: National rate of school completion

Gender/Years	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Boys	16.5%	20.3%	21.7%	23.7%	24.9%	20.4%
Girls	10.9%	14.1%	15.9%	17%	18.7%	16.4%
Total	13.7%	17.8%	18.8%	20.3%	21.8%	18.5%

Source: DRES/Zinder (2020)

In Zinder region, when you take from 2015 to 2020, the rate of pass-repeat-dropout of middle school female students who repeated the year is around 25% but the rate of those who dropped out is around 30% during the same years. This rate which constitutes our third indicator, shows that there is a problem about young girls’ school retention because there is a steady decline in the percentage of girls who pass to the next academic level. Moreover, the rate of girls who dropped out is around 30%, which can be considered as high because almost one third of girls drop out of middle school every year. As far as the repeat rate, it goes up and down from year to year and generally oscillates between 21% and 29.76% (DRES/Zinder, 2021).

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Table 3: Rate of passages-repetition-dropout in middle school in Zinder

Academic years	Middle school					
	Pass %		Repeat %		Dropout %	
	Global	Girls	Global	Girls	Global	Girls
2015-2016	47.28	47.60	23.42	22.90	29.20	29.39
2016-2017	46.46	47.49	24.70	24.29	28.80	28.18
2017-2018	49.22	49.11	22.64	22.73	27.79	28.10
2018-2019	45.82	47.95	26.16	24.56	28.02	27.55
2019-2020	56.17	57.99	22.03	21.27	21.73	20.78
2020-2021	45.08	47.8	30.06	29.76	24.78	22.97

Source: DRES/Zinder (2021)

This study is initiated in view of the studies cited above and the high rates of school repetition and dropout presented in table 3.

Regarding the importance of girl child education mentioned above and the existence of the weak school retention in Zinder, this paper aims to investigate a factor that influences the sustainable girl child education at middle school level of education in rural middle schools.

Objectives of the study

1. Assess the extent of out-of-school students' influence on girl child education at middle schools in mirriah.
2. Assess the extent of unschooled girls influence on girl child education at middle schools in Mirriah.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do out-of-school students influence the girl child education at middle school?
2. To what extent do the unschooled girls influence the girl child education at middle school?

Research Hypotheses

1. The out-of-school girls have no influence on the girl child education at middle school.
2. The unschooled girls have no influence on the girl child education at middle school.

Methodology

The present study was conducted using a qualitative grounded theory design to assess a phenomenon through the interaction and experience of the targeted population. According to Creswell (2012, p.423) "Because a theory is "grounded" in the data, it provides a better explanation than a theory borrowed "off the shelf," because it fits the situation, actually works in practice, is sensitive to individuals in a setting, and may represent all of the complexities actually found in the process". More particularly, this study used a process approach as it is "a sequence of actions and interactions among people and events pertaining to a topic (Corbin & Strauss, 2008 as cited in Creswell 2012, p.431). Mnguni (2014) defines "population" as "a predetermined number of convenient cases that the researcher assumes to be the sample which corresponds to the population of interest. This is what the researcher intends to use to generalize the results of the research" (p. 23). In this study, the population refers to the selected participants who are concerned by the phenomenon of school retention. The respondents for this study consist of seven unschooled girls, seven out-of-school girls, five administrators, and five members of the management Committee of Secondary Education (COGES /ES). These participants are selected purposively according to their social and/or professional place for fighting to keep young girls in school. The data collection instrument used in this study was a direct interview. The data collected in French were translated into English and those collected in the local language were transcribed and then translated into English.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent do out-of-school students influence the girl child education at middle school?

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Table 1 : Statistical analysis on extent to which out-of-school students influence the girl child education at middle school

	Statistiques descriptives		
	N	Moyenne	Ecart type
Do you think that the participation of school girls to the village activities like (traditional week of naming ceremony and marriage) influences the school retention of girls ?	24	3,13	,797
Do you think that the participation of school girls to the village night recreation influences the school attendance of the student?	24	3,42	,717
Are there other activities that influence the girl retention at middle school?	24	1,83	,917
N valide (listwise)	24		

Source: Field data (2023)

The statistical analysis in table 1 showed that $SD < 1$ that means that out-of-school girls have no influence on the girl child education at middle school.

Research Question 2

To what extent do the unschooled girls influence the girl child education at middle school?

Table 2 : Statistical analysis on extent to which unschooled girls influence the girl child education at middle school

	Statistiques descriptives		
	N	Moyenne	Ecart type
Do you think that the participation of school girl to the activities organized by her unschooled peers helps her to remain in school?	24	2,17	,917
Does the desire to belong to a group of unschooled friends push the girl to stay and work hard at school?	24	2,46	,932
Do you think that a female student can be influenced by another unschooled female?	24	3,21	,833
N valide (listwise)	24		

Source : Field data (2023)

The statistical analysis of the second research question in table 2, expresses that the SD is very close to 1, which means the disparity is almost there. However, as $SD < 1$, this can tell us that unschooled girls have a negative influence on the sustainable girl child education at middle school.

Discussion of finding

In view of the above result of statistical analysis of the research question 1, where the results showed that out-of-school girls influence more the girl child education, and these corroborate to the studies carried out by Daniel (2014); Omollo, (2017); and Abdou (2020). Other studies carried out by Johannes, (2018); Abdou, (2020); and Bogosi, (2021) stated the influence of unschooled peers on the sustainable girl child education presented in research question 2 through the table 2 of the statistical analysis.

Conclusion

In general, the phenomenon of sustainable girl child education constitutes a topic of discussion for researchers and educational policy makers. This research discovered that the sustainable education of girls who are studying in rural areas is

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influenced by peers, personal motivation, environment, shared values and beliefs. Findings from research questions revealed that unschooled peer groups do not allow the girl to decide by ‘herself’ in the truest sense of the word. Furthermore, this research revealed the high value placed on social friendships. It is also well established that school girls are highly influenced by out-of-school girls, but they are more highly influenced by unschooled friends. Peer influence has been established to have direct influence on the school attendance of the learner and academic performance. This study found out that students, who were rejected in their class, were negatively affected either emotionally or academically.

Recommendations:

In view of the above findings, the following recommendations should be adopted in order to overcome the issue of peer influence in rural middle schools.

1. The regional teaching office, the departmental teaching office and the girls’ education partners should follow the implementation of the laws carrying the protection and the follow up of girls at middle schools especial the rural ones.
2. The school administration and COGES members should also sensitize the parents and the students on the danger of unschooled and out-of-school peers’ influence.
3. The COGES members should guide students on the importance of carefully choosing friends so that their attitudes towards learning would be improved as the peer group they belong to can have an effect on their learning.
4. The school administration and the COGES should think of organizing periodic school activities for students in order to motivate them.

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